

Effective Using of Speaking Competence of Teaching Foreign Languages in Technical Institutions

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Abstract: The article is devoted to today's globalized world, the demand for teaching and learning is growing. It is the responsibility of every foreign language teacher and every educator to observe new knowledge and attitudes in students. The main goal of teaching a foreign language to students is to acquire basic speech structures corresponding to the level of CEFR competence. Teaching communicative competence is based on topics that meet the real needs and interests of students.

Key words: Demand, Teaching, Growing, Responsibility, Attitude, Competence, Needs, Objective, Features, Formation, Authentic Material

The main goal of teaching a foreign language to students is to acquire basic speech structures corresponding to the level of CEFR competence. Speech training is based on topics that meet the real needs and interests of students. To facilitate communication in students, oral speech includes such specific features of this type of speech activity as motivation, purpose, activity, connection with the personality and mental activity of the individual, heuristics, independence, pace and situation. If there are goals and objectives of communication, taking into account the characteristic features of the participants in the dialogue, their age, level of development, then within the framework of any speech situation, the action of communication will certainly take place.

An important task is to create electronic platforms and resources for Foreign Language teachers and language learners in the developed countries of the world and in the educational system of our country in a foreign language, in particular, English. Of particular importance is the improvement of oral speech competence of language learners, the use of virtual educational technologies pedagogical mechanisms for the development of speech competence. The leading area in the educational activities of students is the educational process. From this, a characteristic feature of the process of professional formation is considered to be a high interest in education, learning. This interest characterizes the specific character of professional qualification formation.

The natural approach and the direct way for teaching foreign languages are quite similar and have many things in common. It emphasizes practice more than the other two approaches to teaching foreign languages. This is quite similar to the language teaching techniques used in classrooms all around the world, where you only use the target language while speaking and use pantomime, visuals, and objects for all other forms of communication.

The direct language learning approach is predicated on the notion that you are learning in the same way you did as a toddler, with no prior knowledge of how to express your thoughts in writing or verbally. In the classroom, there is no translation at all, and when a mistake is made, teachers typically give pupils the option of fixing it on their own. This approach to learning a language aims to get you thinking in that language.

Today, in modern education, it consists in the formation of a multicultural personality, which consists in the formation of their possession of a certain amount of knowledge about a foreign language, the ability not only to understand, but also to communicate freely in it.

The main goal of teaching a foreign language to students is to have basic speech structures corresponding to the threshold level of cognition on the scale of pan - European language competence. The formation of the competence of oral speech is desirable to form based on authentic materials on the needs of language learners and topics that will be appropriate for their interests or future application of the language in practice.

Oral speech-communicative competence covers the grammatical knowledge of the language user, such as syntax, morphology, phonology and the like, but perceives this knowledge as a functional, social concept of how and when to use words correctly.

It is known that the expression of thinking, communication between people, spiritual and other communications are through language. The teacher should pay attention to the features of the educational material, methods of education and educational opportunities in organizing the lesson and increasing the effectiveness of education. This in turn necessitates the widespread introduction of various role-playing games and pedagogical technologies into the educational system during the lesson and cultivates the level of teaching a foreign language, which is reflected in the pedagogical activity of a foreign language teacher.

Each foreign language teacher, based on the above, must have the senses to form his new vision of the educational process. In his activities, the teacher must have a deep knowledge of a foreign language, a deep understanding of talented, modern, scientific and cultural progress, be able to understand the system of knowledge about the world and man from a broad point of view and be able to use computers and internet tools in the educational process, and widely use them in communicative competence.

Many foreign language teachers are faced with the problem of "student slowness" in their lessons in the development of speaking skills in teaching English aimed at special purposes. In order to prevent this, modern pedagogical technologies change the educational situation in such a way that the teacher becomes an attentive and interested interlocutor in the process of cognition. The communicative method, as one of the modern methods of teaching English, helps to ensure that the teacher is not only an information carrier, but also an observer and consultant. The teacher's task is to create educational bilingualism situations that facilitate student communication. The best methods of activating student oral speech are methods of interaction, that is, from interactive techniques, and interactive learning is a method of cognition, it is carried out only under the condition of the joint activities of students. Interactive learning is based on the learning environment, which is an area of experience based on the interaction of students and their psychology. It follows from this that these methods involve the interaction of the subjects of the educational process, where the teacher and the participant are part of the same team, working to achieve the same goal. It should be noted that teaching interactive interaction requires the use of educational materials taken from life in English lessons, which, under properly organized conditions, provides natural communication in the language being studied. Also in the preparation of future engineers, it is advisable for them to develop speech by describing the terminology related to the sphere by pictures, visualization and kinesthetic

To create interactive interaction situations, it is necessary to exclude the limitation of working with tasks that students should imagine themselves in any situation. Terms of relations in a foreign language speech, additional professional texts indicate that knowledge of many types of learning is a requirement of the period. Without degrading the essence of other languages, especially when communicating in English, understanding, reading and writing language speech, in the practice of speech activity, reading broad-based and professional literature by specialty, explaining to them annotations, theses, as well as the importance of information and communication technologies in the processes of written information exchange are clearly and determined.

The application of additional text programs aimed at the educational process is one of the methodological approaches that allow well to adequately solve the issue of teaching English. As a result of the interaction of the teacher and the student, the student will not simply master certain knowledge, but at the same time will again master and lay the foundation for the development of new principles and techniques for doing and actions.

When organizing foreign language lessons, teachers conduct subject-specific surveys, talk about past events, listen to native speakers or describe images. All of these activities are based on the goal of establishing meaningful communication at all language levels using real materials.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the communicative approach is one of the best teaching methods in the study of new languages, an important factor is the adoption of a person who does

not have the ability to communicate in the target language to them and the preparation of students in several dozen lessons in various real situations.

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